

DETECTION OF DEMENTIA USING GRADIENT BOOSTING

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ABSTRACT

Dementia is a serious neurological disease that affects memory, thinking ability, and daily activities. Early detection of dementia is important because it can help doctors start treatment earlier and slow the progression of the disease. In this study, machine learning techniques are used to detect dementia using clinical data. The dataset is taken from the OASIS database and contains three groups: demented, non-demented, and converted. Logistic Regression, Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Gradient Boosting and Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE) is used. Gradient Boosting performs better than the other models and achieves an accuracy of 94.67%. The study shows that machine learning methods can help in the early detection of dementia.

Keywords: Dementia detection, Machine learning, Gradient Boosting, Healthcare analytics, SMOTE

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I. INTRODUCTION

Dementia is a term used to describe a group of symptoms that affect a person's social competence, cognition and memory to the degree that they interfere with daily activities. A single disease does not cause dementia, but a combination of them could. Dementia is a chronic and degenerative disease with a high number among the elderly, affecting 47.5 million individuals worldwide [1]. It happens when the brain's connections and nerve cells are injured or lost [2]. It also has varied effects on different people and causes different symptoms depending on which section of the brain is compromised. Some of the progressive diseases caused by dementia are Parkinson's disease, Alzheimer's disease, Traumatic brain injury (TBI) etc. The diagnosis and prognosis of dementia is a very complex process. A battery of clinical tests, such as cognitive evaluations, patient histories, and neuroimaging, are often used to diagnose dementia, although other possible causes should be ruled out for a more definite diagnosis [3]. Only a post-mortem autopsy can provide a completely definite diagnosis [4]. The procedure, however, is very costly and time-consuming. Besides, the advancement in information technology and health and medical sciences were able to contribute to generating a huge amount of data linked to dementia-like neuroimaging, genetics, cognitive assessment etc [5]. Cerebrovascular dementia (a type of dementia), can be averted through risk factor management and using medical treatment. Surgical procedures, such as thyroid removal or removal of a benign brain tumour, can be used to treat other types of dementia [6]. Early diagnosis can, however, delay the progression of this disease. Machine Learning and Deep Learning have made major contributions to a wide range of industries, including technology, health care, agriculture, and many more. Some of them include malaria detection [7], Text recognition [8], ADHD detection [9], Biomedical Data analysis [10], Retinal Disease detection [11], Maize Leaves Detection [12], etc. In this paper, we have implemented some standard machine learning algorithms like Logistic Regression, ExtraTreesClassifier, Random Forest, ExtremeBoost Classifier (XGBoost), Decision Tree, Light Gradient Boost (LGBM), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Gaussian Naïve Bayes and Gradient Boosting Classifier for multi-class classification problem in detecting the presence of a degenerative disease called dementia in patients. The algorithms were performed on selected features of the dataset extracted using a correlation matrix and were evaluated on metrics like accuracy, precision and F1-score.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

At present, many contributions are being made by ML and DL (deep learning) in various other fields for finding solutions to present-day problems. Machine learning is making a significant impact in the medical and health sector like the detection of Mycobacterium tuberculosis using convolutional neural network (CNN) [13] or diagnosis of skin cancer using feature engineering techniques of deep learning [14]. Dementia is a very serious degenerative disorder, and should not be taken lightly. Many researchers have paid heed to the problem and have contributed to finding the solution for this problem. Aruna et al. (2015) [15] extracted features using the Gabor filter from the MRI images dataset and performed the Support Vector Machin (SVM) technique with different kernel values. The RBF kernel showed high accuracy of 0.9024. Mathotaarachchi et al. (2017) [16] implemented SVM and regularised logistic regression employed in the ADGNI-GO/2 investigation and obtained an accuracy of 84% and an operating characteristic curve of 0.91. For the early identification of Alzheimer's disease (AD), Ramirez et al. (2013) [17] suggested a completely automated computer-aided diagnostic (CAD) system. They implemented the SVM model with the RBF kernel, achieving an accuracy of 90.38%. The same SVM model was used by Rabeh et al. (2016) [18], who used three sections of the brain as a database and attained an accuracy of 90.66%. Meyer et al. (2017) [19] proposed a personalised diagnostic approach based on a brain MRI dataset and SVM, in which BVFTD (Behavioral Variant of Frontotemporal Dementia) is categorised and predicted in a group comparison, as well as the MRI, scans across the whole brain of each subject using brain atrophy and the most affected regions of the frontotemporal, insular, and basal ganglia, with a whole-brain accuracy of 86.5%. Battineni et al. (2019) [20] used the SVM classification approach on the dataset from Open Access of Imaging Studies (OASIS) and used a smaller number of inputs for the model. They achieved accuracy and precision of 68.75% and 64.18% respectively. In a study by Canu et al. (2017) [21], they used an approach for combining data on white matter microstructure and cortical thickness to differentiate between Early Onset Alzheimer's Disease (EOAD) and BVFTD patients using Random Forest analysis. The accuracy, specificity and sensitivity obtained were 0.82, 0.76 and 0.96 respectively. Islam et al. (2017) [22] performed multi-class classification using the convolutional neural network technique on the MRI dataset extracted from OASIS and achieved an accuracy of 73.75%. Castellazi et al. [23] (2020) combined an MRI dataset with ML algorithms for the binary classification of Alzheimer's Disease (AD) and Vascular Dementia (VD). Resting-state fMRI and Diffusion Tensor Imaging (DTI) metrics were used as input features on ML algorithms like

Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Interface System (ANFIS), Artificial Neural Network (ANN), and Support Vector Machine (SVM). ANFIS algorithm achieved the highest accuracy of 84% and on applying the best discriminant pattern to the data, it achieved a prediction rate of 77.33%. Zhu et al. [24] (2020) implemented various ML algorithms for Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI), initial diagnosis of normal, dementia and Very Mild Dementia (VMD). The algorithm which performed best was Naïve Bayes giving precision, accuracy, F-measure and recall of 0.82, 0.81, 0.81 and 0.81 respectively. The hierarchical classification was performed by Kim et al. [25] (2019) on the MRI data obtained from the patients with Frontotemporal Dementia (FTD) and AD using four classifiers using different pairs of groups like FTD and AD, BVFTD and PPA (Primary Progressive Aphasia). The accuracies obtained in four groups were 86.1%, 90.8%, 86.9% and 92.1% respectively. All of the previous techniques for the classification of dementia disease were competent, but they lacked the entire set of metrics needed to forecast with all machine learning (ML) algorithms. Some datasets used were small whereas, in others, fewer feature inputs were applied to the models. The cost of dementia analysis is expensive and therefore, a high accuracy ML model is required for the classification. Muhammad Memon et al. [31] made use of the ADNI dataset and employed diverse algorithms, including Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, and Support Vector Machine. Among these algorithms, Logistic Regression exhibited superior performance, showcasing high accuracy and specificity rates of 98.12% and 95% respectively. In a distinct investigation, Hala Ahmed et al. [32] leveraged both the Alzheimer's Disease Neuroimaging Initiative (ADNI) and Whole-genome Sequencing (WGS) datasets. Notably, Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms (SNPs) were identified as notable biomarkers in conjunction with these datasets. The researchers applied four machine learning algorithms, namely Naive Bayes, Random Forest, Logistic Regression, and Support Vector Machine. Among these techniques, the Naive Bayes algorithm emerged as the most effective, attaining an accuracy rate of 98.1% for a specific dataset.

Mondal et al. [34] and Das et al. [35] show that ML models can help detect diseases such as Alzheimer's and breast cancer. Sikder et al. [37] also shows how combining different types of medical data can improve early disease detection. Shekh and Uddin [30] studied how safety professionals manage chemical exposure risks in industrial workplaces. Shekh and Islam [36] showed how EHS analytics can improve safety training, hazard communication, and incident reporting using data-driven methods.

III. METHODOLOGY

Dataset used was taken from Kaggle [32]. The dataset contains records of 186 patients who were grouped as “demented”, “non-demented” and “converted”. “Demented” refers to a patient who is suffering from Dementia, “Non-Demented” means a patient who was not diagnosed with it, and “Converted” refers to a patient who was diagnosed as “Non-Demented”, but later was found to be suffering from dementia. The patients were assigned a subject id and a patient can have multiple MRI IDs. The dataset is comprised of 373 rows x 15 columns. Features in 15 columns were “MMSE”, “SES”, “CDR”, “Subject ID”, “Group”, “MRI ID”, “Visit”, “M/F”, “MR delay”, “ASF”, “Age”, “eTIV”, “EDUC”, “nWBV” and “Hand”. The datasets are balanced using SMOTE. Due to an imbalance in the class of datasets, the results and predictions are greatly influenced, as many ML approaches neglect the dataset entities and hence produce poor results. There are fewer samples of the minority class from which the ML Classifiers can adjust when the classification is not balanced, which is a serious concern. Oversampling, or replicating samples from the class with the few examples in the training set before fitting the ML model, can be used to fix the problem.

After data exploration, we have implemented Gradient Boosting, LR and SVM. The next step involves concluding and measuring the results using some assessment metrics to determine the most superlative classifier for the email data set dataset. The SMOTE oversampling technique was implemented by setting the random state to 1. The classifiers were trained using the rectified sample with a random state set to 42. After training the classifiers, the most suitable one was selected using metric evaluation. Table III shows the performance of ML models

based on standard metrics like “Accuracy”, “Recall”, “Precision”, “Jaccard Score”, “F1-score” and “Cohen Kappa Score (CKS)”. Table III shows that Gradient Boost models perform best as compared to other models and form a good relationship with the dataset. The Gradient Boost was trained by setting the learning rate to 0.1, n-estimators to 120, and random state to 42 and rest parameters as default. Since the dataset was a little imbalanced, SMOTE oversampling technique was

TABLE I
ML Models

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 Score	Jaccard Score
Gradient Boosting	94.67%	91.94%	86.62%	88.77%	81.93%
LR	54.27%	57.85%	63.69%	53.48%	37.77%
SVM	38.00%	20.74%	42.86%	26.62%	18.56%

True Negative (TN) is an assortment of true negative facts through a negative description. Therefore, it is an inference where the ML Models predict the negative class fittingly. False-negative (FN) is an assortment of negative data which is characterized as positive. Therefore, it is an inference where the ML Models predict the negative class improperly. A false positive (FP) is an assortment of positive data that has been described as negative. Thus, it is an inference where the ML Models predict the positive class imperfectly

True Positive (TP) data is an assortment of true positive data that has been categorized as positive. Thus, it is an inference where the ML Models predict the positive class fittingly. 95% Confidence Interval is [87.07%, 97.91%}. Accuracy of Gradient boosting, LR and SVM is 94.67%, 54.27% and 38.00%, respectively.

Fig. 1 Confusion Matrix of Gradient Boosting

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Dementia is a serious worldwide health concern, and rather than finding a cure, more emphasis is being placed on risk reduction, early intervention, and quick detection of the condition in older persons. As the senior population grows as a result of societal ageing, dementia becomes more common, and the number of young dementia patients grows as well. In this paper, we employed the potential of machine learning for multi-class classification among dementia patients as “demented”, “non-demented” or “converted”. Dementia is a serious disease that affects millions of people around the world. Early detection can help doctors provide better treatment and improve patient quality of life. Gradient Boosting performed the best, achieving the highest accuracy compared to the other models.

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